

Poisson Blanc Regional Park Ecological Monitoring Program Indicator Proposal

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Executive Summary

The Poisson Blanc Regional Park, hereafter referred to as the Park, is located in Quebec, Canada, and welcomes 35 000 users every year across the 60 campsites they manage on the Poisson Blanc Reservoir. The Watershed Stewardship Research Collaborative (WSRC) is an academic research team based out of Carleton University, in Ottawa, Canada, focused on freshwater conservation. These two groups have partnered to develop a custom ecological monitoring program for the Park. This program will provide managers with a better understanding of the ecological status of the territory they manage, how it responds to the Park's recreational and tourism use, as well as to the management actions that are implemented in the Park.

This document showcases a preliminary list of 24 indicators recommended for the Park's new ecological monitoring program. This list was developed by the research team with input from park staff and other local stakeholders. It is based on indicators measured in other existing monitoring programs, as well as information about the local context of the Poisson Blanc Regional Park. Together, the recommended indicators will allow the Park to keep track of various aspects of human impact, ecosystem status, biodiversity and water quality. The list will be assessed by park management to decide which indicators should and can be measured during the first iteration of their new ecological monitoring program, which will be implemented in the summer of 2024.

Why implement an ecological monitoring program?

Parks can make significant contributions to human well-being by providing spaces to recreate and connect with nature. They can also foster ecological integrity, which feeds back into the sustainable provision of various natural resources such as clean water. Furthermore, parks can contribute to the conservation of biodiversity by safeguarding high quality habitat. However, many parks do not have programs in place that allow them to track these contributions. This type of tracking is beneficial, as it can help improve understanding of the socio-ecological implications of having a park in place, as well as provide information regarding how an area is changing through time, and whether or not alternative management strategies are needed to sustainably achieve conservation and human well-being objectives. Ecological monitoring programs can help track such information through the measurement of ecological indicators.

Ecological monitoring programs can be costly and complicated to implement, leaving many parks without such programs. Partnerships between parks and academic research teams able to help develop such programs are one avenue to decrease barriers associated with the implementation of ecological monitoring programs. The collaboration referred to in this document seeks to demonstrate such an approach, all the while serving as a resource for other parks.

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Explanation of the Categorization of Indicators

An ecological indicator provides information on an ecological process or pattern, and is measured to provide insights into the ecological status of a system and how it changes through time. The indicators recommended for this monitoring program are nested within two major themes: indicators that reflect anthropogenic (i.e. human) stressors, or indicators that reflect ecosystem components.

Anthropogenic stressor: Unnatural effects and characteristics caused by human activity. These stress factors can disrupt the functioning of an ecosystem.

Ecosystem component: A natural process or component that occurs within an ecosystem. Although human interactions can influence the rate and extent to which these processes occur, an ecosystem component would continue to operate in the absence of human activity.

The indicators are then further categorized by parameter, which describe the broader process that each indicator measures. The proposed indicators measure four parameters: direct human impact, ecosystem status, biodiversity and water quality.

Direct human impact: A measure of the impacts on an ecosystem that are the direct result of human activity.

Ecosystem status: A measure of characteristics that explain ecological processes operating within an ecosystem.

Biodiversity: A measure of the characteristics of an ecosystem that provide information on the presence, absence and diversity of species.

Water quality: A measure of various biological, physical or chemical components of water.

Every indicator included in the proposed monitoring program is nested within a theme and a parameter. Several different indicators can be used to measure the same parameter and parameters can have indicators of different themes.

Breaking Down the Word 'Indicator'

Breakdown of Content on Each Individual Indicator Page

Name of indicator

Theme	Parameter	Cost
See page 5	See page 5	\$: \$0-10 \$\$: \$10-300 \$\$\$: \$300-1000

Cost of equipment and laboratory analysis: The estimated cost of equipment required to measure a specific indicator. Some indicators share equipment and the equipment piece will only need to be purchased once. Shared equipment is not taken into account for the individual indicator, and the cost represents the entire cost of measuring an indicator.

Description: Key information on the indicator and why there is value in measuring it.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
How often the indicator needs to be measured.	The primary tools required to monitor this indicator.

Summary of methods: A brief description of the process involved with monitoring this indicator.

Potential related management actions: If campsite area is found to increase over time, the Park could consider establishing area borders which encourage visitors to stay within their designated campsite area. If there is found to be a large discrepancy between campsite areas on sites that offer the same amenities (e.g. same number of tent spots), the Park could consider restoring parts of larger campsites.

Labour requirements for park staff: How many park staff are required to measure a specific indicator and can the indicator be measured within a park staff's existing workday given current workflow? If the indicator can not be measured within a work day, how many hours will the measurement take park staff to complete.

External support requirements: Does the measurement of a specific indicator require a service that is beyond the scope of the Park? If so, what level of support is needed? Additional support may be provided by the research team, or by consulting a specialist or laboratory services (i.e., laboratory analysis of samples).

Management implications: How the Park can benefit from monitoring this indicator. What the Park can do with the information gained from monitoring this indicator.

Client engagement opportunity: How clients can become involved with the process of monitoring this indicator.

Direct Human Impact

Campsite Area

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$

Description: Campsite area can be broken into two parts: periphery area and activity area. The activity area is the part of a site with no vegetation cover and clear signs of human activity (e.g. fire pit, tent platform, toilet). The peripheral area is part of a site that surrounds the activity area; it maintains some vegetation cover but there are signs of management. Unintentional increases in campsite area over time indicate an unnecessary expansion of human footprint that should be avoided.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 5 years	GPS, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: The research team will use a GPS to delineate the periphery and area activity of each campsite, as well as mark key campsite features (e.g. tent spot, toilet, etc.). Geographic information system processing will then be used to calculate area measurements for each campsite.

Potential related management actions: If campsite area is found to increase over time, the Park could consider establishing area borders which encourage visitors to stay within their designated campsite area. If there is found to be a large discrepancy between campsite areas on sites that offer the same amenities (e.g. same number of tent spots), the Park could consider restoring parts of larger campsites.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member working an 8 hour day to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Mallikage et al. (2021); Carletto et al. (2016)

Length of Redundant Trails

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$

Description: Redundant trails are considered to be separate trails that lead to the same place. A portion of a given trail network that has redundancy could be restored to increase vegetation cover.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 2 years	GPS, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: Within the established boundary of each campsite, a member of the research team will walk the full extent of each established trail while holding a GPS. Segments of, or entire trails, will be categorized as “redundant” if they lead to the same place as another existing segment of the trail network or “novel” if the trail is unique to its start and end point. The geospatial information of site trails will be used to identify the number and length (m) of redundant trails at each campsite.

Potential related management actions: Following the initial evaluation, the Park could consider regenerating/restoring redundant components of trails (e.g. plant trees to increase a site’s carbon storage capacity).

Client engagement opportunities: If the Park decides to remediate the trail sections classified as redundant, clients could be given the opportunity to help with this effort by planting trees at their campsite. The seedlings would be distributed by the Park and planting areas would be clearly defined at the site.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following baseline survey. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

Human Markings on Trees

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$

Description: Human markings are any unnatural physical damage that a tree has endured resulting from a human action. Markings include carving into wood (e.g. initials), hacking (e.g. axe marks), bark pulling, and branch pulling. This damages the tree and creates weak spots where bacteria can enter a tree and cause further damage.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Annually	Tablet (on site data entry), GPS, ruler, camera

Summary of methods: The trees that lie within the established boundaries of each campsite boundary and along Park trails that have markings will be geolocated and assigned a score based on the extent of damage endured by the tree. At campsites, the proportion of damaged trees will be compared to the overall number of trees (as calculated in carbon storage potential indicator). The initial measurement of this indicator will be taken by a member of the research team, subsequent measurements will be carried out by park staff.

Potential related management actions: If markings increase through time the Park can install information posters about why it is important not to mark trees and document if this helps. Existing research has excellent recommendations for most effective signage strategies.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following baseline survey. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Leung and Marion (1999); Morin et al. (2016)

Trail Width

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: The width of a trail is measured as the distance (cm) across the length of a trail that is not covered by vegetation and has a clear border created by recreational use or signage. Measuring this over time is important to ensure that recreational use is not unnecessarily extending trails into unintended ecosystems.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Annually	Measuring tape or ruler, pocket level, poles (4), white string, scissors, measuring wheel, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: Trail width will be measured at three separate locations along a minimum of one established trail at each campsite. Sampled locations will be marked to allow for inter-annual comparison. The initial measurement of this indicator will be taken by a member of the research team, subsequent measurements will be carried out by a park staff.

Potential related management actions: If trail width is found to increase over time, the Park could consider establishing clear trail borders which encourage visitors to stay on the trails.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Marion and Leung (2011)

Exposed Roots on Trails

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: Tree roots can become exposed through various erosional processes, including natural ones such as rain, or human induced ones such as trail use (hiking, biking, ATV). Measuring the number of roots exposed along a trail can help determine the degree of erosion a trail has endured, and if this trail needs to be closed and restored for a period of time to ensure its long term sustainability.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 2 years	Tablet (on site data entry), measuring tape, metal markers, measuring wheel, white string, camera

Summary of methods: Exposed roots will be measured along trails within campsites. A member of the research team will walk along established trails to identify the area of greatest root exposure. From the centre of this area, a 1m square will be sampled to document the number and length of each exposed root. This measurement will be repeated along three randomly selected trails at every campsite managed by the Park. Sampled locations will be marked with a discrete metal marker to allow precise inter-annual comparison.

Potential related management actions: The Park could consider remediating trails to help recover from soil loss due to erosion. This will help maintain trail conditions and protect surrounding vegetation from further eroding and trail widening. In cases of high root exposure, the Park could implement structures to alleviate pressures from roots caused by erosion and trampling, these structures could also improve visitor safety by reducing risk of tripping over exposed roots.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Marion and Leung (2011); Mallikage et al. (2021)

Soil Compaction

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$

Description: Soil gets compacted when pressure is applied to the soil surface, removing air spaces within a soil layer. Compaction makes it difficult for plant roots to grow and water to get absorbed. Human activity (walking, biking, driving) compacts soil and should be monitored to ensure the compaction takes place only in designated areas to avoid harm to surrounding habitats. Soil compaction can be measured by the soil density or by its resistance to penetration by either water or force (force required to push an object into the soil).

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 2 years at closing	Pocket penetrometer, measuring wheel, GPS, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: Soil compaction will be measured at three separate locations along a minimum of one established trail at each campsite. Sampled locations will be marked to allow for inter-annual comparison. The initial measurement of this indicator will be taken by a member of the research team, subsequent measurements will be carried out by park staff.

Potential related management actions: The Park could remediate trails and the campsite area to help recover from soil loss due to erosion. This will help maintain trail conditions and protect surrounding vegetation from further eroding and trail widening. Research shows remediation is most effective following heavy rain.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover or closure workday.

External support requirements: Research team member.

References: Marion and Cole (1996); Marion and Leung (2011); Mallikage et al. (2021)

Boat Use

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: Boat use monitors the extent to which park boats are used to complete work related tasks. Measures of distance travelled and the fuel consumed will provide information required to evaluate the efficiency and cost (fuel and staff) of services offered by the park.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Fuel log to be filled every time a boat is filled up with fuel	Tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: Every time that a boat is filled with fuel, the volume of fuel used since the last filling will be recorded.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to record fuel use. This measurement fits within any workday where the boats are filled with fuel.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

Firewood Consumption

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: Firewood consumption estimates the volume of carbon dioxide released from campfires during a client’s stay. The objective of measuring this indicator is to quantify the carbon footprint of campfires. Information from this indicator will estimate the environmental impact of campfires.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Weekly, on one of the campsite visitor turnover days	Tablet (on site data entry), calculator

Summary of methods: On campsite visitor turnover days, a park staff will record the number of bags of wood left over to determine the amount of wood burnt. The number will be entered into a spreadsheet, containing a formula set up by a member of the research team, which will calculate the mass of carbon dioxide emitted and estimate the carbon footprint of fire pit use at each site after each client visits.

Potential related management actions: If the results from monitoring this indicator show that clients are not using all of the wood provided or that the volume of CO₂ generated from campfires is found to be greater than the emission targets of the park, the Park could offer a tiered service where clients can decide the amount of wood that they would like and whether they would like this delivered or if they would like to carry it themselves.

Client engagement activities: Clients can reduce the amount of fuel that the Park uses by decreasing the quantity of wood that they use or by deciding to carry their own firewood to their site.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to record left over wood. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

Garbage Accumulated After a Trip by Guests

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: This measures the total weight of waste (organics, recycling, garbage) generated by a group after a visit to the park. Values will be used to identify the sustainability of guests and determine if a waste-reduction strategy should be implemented.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 3 years, 3 days throughout the summer season	Scale

Summary of methods: A member of the research team will set up a weighing station designed for visitors use following a trip. Clients will be directed to the voluntary station where a member of the research team will weigh their garbage and then dispose of the waste for them. This measurement will be carried out on a checkout day following the weekend three times throughout the summer season.

Potential related management actions: Some clients may generate more waste than others. After initial measurements, the Park could use the lowest amount of waste generated per person as a goal for other visitors to achieve. The Park could develop resources that demonstrate how clients can create less waste during their stay at the Park.

Client engagement activities: The Park could provide clients with solutions to reducing their waste while canoe camping. Using such resources, clients would learn and have the opportunity to practice Zero Waste principles.

External support requirements: Research team member.

Garbage Found at the Campsite

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$

Description: Garbage such as food wrappers, water bottles, and toilet paper, left behind by people, cause damage to wildlife through consumption and can in also result in lasting ecosystem level pollution. Monitoring this can support the establishment of signage or improve waste disposal infrastructure along trails.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Campsite visitor turnover days	Tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: On campsite visitor turnover days, park staff will conduct a scan of the campsite and collect any garbage present. They will record information about this garbage in a log.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to collect and record garbage. This measurement fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Mallikage et al. (2021)

Pathogen Content of Human Waste in Operating Pit Toilets

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$\$

Description: Fecal matter contains pathogens that can persist well after they are deposited if conditions are unfavourable (e.g. wet, cold, compact). Pathogen content poses a health risk as fecal matter decomposes and joins underlying soil. If the pathogens have not decayed, there is contamination risk to the surrounding soil and water.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 5 years	Sampling supplies (assembled by the research team), personal protective equipment

Summary of methods: The content within toilet pits will be sampled by a member of the research team. Samples will be taken at six campsites for three depths. Samples will be sent to a laboratory for analysis of the pathogen content.

Potential related management actions: Following the initial measurement of this indicator, the Park could consider changing the depth of pits, depending on the degree of contamination. The Park could also consider changing the toilet style, implement steps to increase pathogen decay (e.g. aerating the material stored in the pit toilets).

External support requirements: Research team member, lab for analysis.

References: Capone et al. (2021); Musaazi et al. (2023)

Pathogen Content of Human Waste in Retired Pit Toilets

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Direct human impact	\$\$\$

Description: Fecal matter contains pathogens that can persist well after they are deposited if conditions are unfavourable (e.g. wet, cold, compact). Pathogen content poses a health risk as fecal matter decomposes and joins underlying soil. If the pathogens have not decayed, there is contamination risk to the surrounding soil and water.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 5 years	Sampling supplies (assembled by the research team), personal protective equipment

Summary of methods: A member of the research team will locate and sample retired pit toilets. Samples will be taken at six campsites for three depths. Samples will be sent to a laboratory for analysis of the pathogen content.

Potential related management actions: If retired sites are found to have high pathogen levels, the Park could consider soil remediation efforts. If the pathogen content in retired toilet sites are found to surpass health standards set by the Quebec Government, the Park could consider actions to increase pathogen decay in operating toilets to eliminate the risk of contamination at retired sites.

External support requirements: Research team member, lab for analysis.

References: Capone et al. (2021); Musaazi et al. (2023)

Ecosystem Status

Trees Vulnerable to Collapse

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Ecosystem status	\$\$

Description: Trees become vulnerable to collapse when underlying soil de-stabilises and the tree rooting system has nothing to hold on to. Monitoring this can promote visitor safety by knowing which trees are likely to collapse.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Baseline survey conducted every 5 years, monitoring of high risk trees will receive annual check-ups in the spring when sites prepared for opening	Tablet (on site data entry), hazard evaluation sheet, diameter tape, hand lenses, binoculars, sounding mallet, insect and disease field identification guides

Summary of methods: A member of the research team will walk the outer perimeter of the campsite, the perimeter of site amenities, and all visible trails. During this survey, the researcher will evaluate all trees taller than 1.5m with a diameter at breast height (DBH) of over 10cm that boarder the site amenities and perimeter according to the Hazard Tree Identification form. The researcher will then evaluate all trees taller than 1.5m with a DBH of over 15cm within a 2m boundary of the campsite perimeter. Trees with increasing DBH that lie beyond the 2m boundary will also be measured until the the researcher is 15m away from the campsite perimeter. Once the baseline data is collected, subsequent measurements will be carried out by park staff.

Potential related management actions: Trees of high failure potential will be monitored regularly and trimmed or removed when necessary.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member working an 8 hour day to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Angwin et al. (2012)

Campsite Carbon Storage (Via Live Woody Plants)

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Ecosystem status	\$\$

Description: Carbon storage is an important process that mediates the volume of carbon dioxide present in the atmosphere as a greenhouse gas. Trees are very good at capturing carbon. Campsite carbon storage via live woody plants is a measure of the carbon stored by all live woody plants (i.e. mainly trees) that lie within the boundaries of campsites managed by the Park.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 5 years	GPS, calculator, diameter tape, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: A member of the research team will survey the live woody plants taller than 1.5m with a diameter at breast height (DBH) of over 1cm established within each campsite. Each plant will be identified (to the species level) and DBH will be measured. Further calculations will be done offsite to calculate each campsite’s carbon storage via live woody plants.

Potential related management actions: Following the initial measurement of this indicator, the Park could implement a regeneration effort (e.g. tree planting) targeted at sites with lower than average live woody plant carbon storage.

Client engagement activities: The Park could engage clients to help with a regeneration effort. This could be done by providing clients with sapplings to plant on their trip for designated sites that have lower carbon storage potential than the mean.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member working an 8 hour day to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Ziter et al. (2013); Hanna et al. (2020)

Composition of Understory Vegetation Surrounding Trails

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$\$

Description: Understory vegetation refers to the vegetation that grows between the forest floor and forest canopy. In this context, composition measures the number and type of species present within defined area, and provides a measure of biodiversity. Recreational activities can decrease the viability of habitat, therefore, measuring the composition of understory vegetation surrounding trails offers information on how recreation impacts habitat quality.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Twice a season, every 2 years: 1x in spring and 1x in fall	GPS, metal markers, plant identification guide, tablet (on site data entry)

Summary of methods: A member of the research team will survey understory vegetation using study plots that boarder established trails within each campsite, three plots along three separate trails will be evaluated per site. The vegetation lying within the plot will be surveyed and their information (i.e. richness, evenness, abundance) will be recorded.

Potential related management actions: Following the initial measurement of this indicator, the Park could implement barriers or clear trail borders to prevent damage to vegetation in areas of lower vegetation surrounding trails.

Client engagement activities: Clients can contribute to the Park’s iNaturalist profile, as described in the plant presence indicator.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member working an 8 hour day to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team.

External support requirements: Research team member.

References: Atik et al. (2009); Ballantyne and Pickering (2015); Abe et al. (2021)

Erosion Potential of a Bank

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Ecosystem status	\$\$

Description: Erosion potential evaluates the likelihood of collapse caused by erosion processes (e.g. rain, changes in reservoir water level, walking). It is measured based on characteristics related to erosion (e.g. bank height, root density, surface protection) that are combined to assign an erosion potential score to a given area and can be used to identify areas that should be blocked off from recreational use for restoration.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 2 years	GPS, tablet with the modified erosion index sheet (on site data entry), wooden poles, measuring wheel, ruler

Summary of methods: Using methods outlined in the modified BEHI (Bank Erosion Hazard Index) procedure the research team will measure four indicators of erosion at 10 randomly selected campsites. Measures will be taken in the spring and fall in 5m areas alongside a visitor access path and contrasted with measures taken at equivalently sized undisturbed portions of the shoreline. Note that visitor access paths are defined as the areas that the park intends for visitors to use to access campsites, these are typically areas with milder slopes and less vegetation than the rest of the shoreline. At sites with multiple access paths the largest one will be measured.

Potential related management actions: After the initial evaluation, park staff could visit sites that scored poorly on the BEHI and determine if management intervention is needed. Overtime, if sites endure a drastic change, the Park could consider closing or relocating the site to allow time for remediation.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member working an 8 hour day to complete subsequent measurements following the baseline survey completed by the research team.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Newton and Drenten (2015)

Water Quality

RSVL and IQBP Indicators of Water Quality

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Anthropogenic stressor	Water quality	\$\$\$

Description : Contaminants can be introduced to water bodies from human sources and natural processes. Various indicators are used in Quebec (e.g. IQBP) to evaluate water quality based on the presence of major contaminants and concentrations of various components of water quality. Information about the combined concentrations of these measurements determines the water’s safety for use (e.g. drinking, swimming , aquatic life).

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Annual	Water sampling equipment (assembled by the research team)

Summary of methods: Using the two pre-established sampling stations in the reservoir, water samples will be collected three times per summer by a member of the research team following the dates and protocol established by the RSVL (Réseau de surveillance volontaire des lacs). Additional samples will be collected in accordance with methods used for the calculation of the IQBP (Indice de la qualité bactériologique et physicochimique de l’eau). Water samples will be delivered to the Ville de Gatineau Laboratoire within 48 hours of sampling and analyzed for chlorophyll a, dissolved organic carbon, total phosphorous, total dissolved solids, fecal coliform, nitrite and nitrate, and ammonia and ammonium concentrations. Secchi depth will be recorded on site. This sampling will fulfill the RSVL protocol and allow for a rough calculation of the IQBP.

Potential related management actions: If there is a negative change in water quality over time, the Park could work with other local stakeholders to determine and implement solutions.

Client engagement opportunities: Have “Water Rangers” water quality sampling kits available to borrow at the Park reception for clients that are interested in learning and participating in water quality monitoring.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to complete subsequent measurements following baseline survey. This measurement fits within a campsite turn-over workday.

External support requirements: Research team member, lab for analysis.

References: MELCC and CRE Laurentides (2017); MELCC (2022)

Biodiversity

Presence of Invasive Plant Species

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$

Description: Invasive species are non-native invasive species that can outcompete native species and cause disturbances to the entire ecosystem. Tracking the presence and distribution of invasive species is useful to determine the risk of an invasion. It is difficult to relieve the pressure of an invasion once it is well established and monitoring invasives can prevent a species establishment.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Initial baseline survey, to be repeated every 5 years. Ongoing record from client observations	Tablet (on site data entry), camera for ID later, species identification field guide, iNaturalist project

Summary of methods: During the initial survey of each campsite, a member of the research team will scan the entire campsite area for locally relevant invasive plant species (i.e. list provided by the Invasive Species Centre). If any species are found, their location and abundance will be recorded so that the species establishment can be monitored annually by Park staff. Clients will also be able to report sightings through the iNaturalist Park project.

Potential related management actions: If the establishment of an invasive species is discovered, the Park could intervene and consider removing the plant entirely.

Client engagement opportunities: The Park could post signage indicating what invasive species to look for. The signs could include a QR code that links to the Park’s iNaturalist profile, where clients can log sightings.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement and iNaturalist project set up.

References: Oettel and Lapin (2021)

Wild Edible Plants

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$

Description: Wild edible plants are plants found in nature that are safe for human consumption. Foraging for wild edibles was a common source of food before the rise in agriculture, making them a traditional and culturally important aspect of human life. Wild edibles are a provisioning ecosystem service and are beneficial in many ways (i.e., economic value, provide people with a sense of place, recreation opportunity). Tracking and reporting the state of wild edibles that exist on campsites sets the stage for sustainable interactions between these plants and clients.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Initial baseline survey, to be repeated every 5 years. Ongoing record from client observations	List of edible plants found in south-western Quebec, GPS, camera

Summary of methods: During the initial survey of each site, a member of the research team will scan the entire campsite area for edible plants using a field guide and list of known edible plants in the area. If any species are found, their location and abundance will be recorded. Clients will also be able to report sightings through the iNaturalist Park project.

Potential related management actions: If abundance diminishes over time conservation strategies (e.g. signage) could be used to help preserve edibles.

Client engagement opportunities: The Park could consider providing clients with a list of wild edibles found across the Park and guidelines on sustainable foraging practices to avoid over harvesting.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement and iNaturalist project set up.

References: Schulp et al. (2014)

Animal Presence

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$

Description: Observations of animal tracks and animal sightings can provide an estimate of the presence of animals and the biodiversity of a specific area. Maintaining a log of documented animal tracks and sightings allows the Park to track changes over time and address recorded changes. Park clients are the primary users engaged in the measurement of this indicator, using iNaturalist.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Ongoing record from client observations	N/A

Summary of methods: The research team will create an iNaturalist project for the Park and surrounding forests. Clients will be able to download the iNaturalist app and record plant and animal observations throughout their visit to the Park. Client observations will form a database of presence data that will be tracked through this online platform.

Potential related management actions: If a rare or endangered species is identified (see COSEWIC list) consequential management actions should be considered.

Client engagement opportunities: The Park could consider creating signage indicating what species to look for and where to find them. The signs could include a QR code that links to the Park’s iNaturalist profile, where clients can log sightings. The Park could also advertise their iNaturalist project to clients through their website, newsletter or upon campsite reservation.

External support requirements: Research team member for iNaturalist project set up.

References: Aceves-Bueno (2015); Mamun and Natcher (2023)

Plant Presence

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$

Description: Observations of plants can estimate the biodiversity that the Park supports. Maintaining a log of documented plant species allows the Park to track changes over time and address recorded changes. Park clients are the primary users engaged in the measurement of this indicator, using iNaturalist.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Ongoing record from client observations	N/A

Summary of methods: The research team will create an iNaturalist project for the Park and surrounding forests. Clients will be able to download the iNaturalist app and record plant and animal observations throughout their visit to the Park. Client observations will form a database of presence data that will be tracked through this online platform.

Potential related management actions: If a rare or endangered species is identified (see COSEWIC list) consequential management actions should be considered.

Client engagement opportunities: The Park could consider creating signage indicating what species to look for and where to find them. The signs could include a QR code that links to the Park’s iNaturalist profile, where clients can log sightings. The Park could also advertise their iNaturalist project to clients through their website, newsletter or upon campsite reservation.

External support requirements: Research team member for iNaturalist project set up.

References: Aceves-Bueno (2015); Abe et al. (2021); Mamun and Natcher (2023)

Benthic Invertebrate Diversity

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$\$\$

Description: Benthic invertebrates (e.g. dragonfly larvae, clams, worms) are water bugs that live on and in the bottom sediments of a waterbody. They are commonly used as indicators of overall aquatic health and play an important role in food chains as they are prey for fish and birds. Measures of their diversity assess the abundance of different types of species that are present in a system. This indicator is useful to evaluate ecosystem health and stability over time from an aquatic biodiversity perspective.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 3 years	GPS, sampling supplies (assembled by the research team)

Summary of methods: Benthic invertebrate diversity will be measured by a member of the research team at the visitor access path and nearby undisturbed shoreline of 10 campsites by collecting benthic invertebrates using methods outlined in Jones 2011. Individual insects in samples will be identified via microscopy and composite measures of benthic invertebrate diversity that can be compared through time will be calculated (e.g. how many different species were present? where these mainly pollution tolerant or sensitive species? what were their abundances?).

Potential related management actions: If there is a significant difference in diversity between visitor access paths and undisturbed shoreline the Park could consider limiting the size of visitor access paths as much as possible. If a decrease in pollution intolerant species is observed through time, the Park will know it must work to restore shoreline habitat complexity.

Client engagement opportunities: Have “MacroBlitz” sampling kits available to borrow at the Park reception for clients that are interested in learning about macro invertebrates or adding observations of macro invertebrates to iNaturalist. Clients can follow “MacroBlitz” protocols to record their observations using iNaturalist and link these to the Park iNaturalist project.

External support requirements: Research team member, lab for analysis.

References: Jones (2011)

Bird Presence

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$\$\$

Description: Monitoring avian presence across an ecosystem is useful for evaluating habitat change and disturbances. Bird presence is monitoring using technologies like acoustic recorders, as well as observations made by park visitors and staff.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Ongoing during periods of peak bird activity (i.e. dusk and dawn) over the course of the summer season. Ongoing by visitors	Audio moth, batteries, microSD cards, identification software

Summary of methods: The research team will install audio recorders at random sites distributed throughout the Park which are programmed to record during times of high bird activity. The recorders will be installed at permanent locations by the research team. The research team will monitor and collect from these for the first year of the program, but in following years the recorders will be serviced by a Park staff on monthly basis between April and October. A member of the research team will annually run the recordings through an identification software in order to identify present bird species.

Client engagement opportunities: The Park could share findings with clients and provide annual updates on the bird species found within the Park. Bird watchers and other outdoor enthusiasts may be interested in the bird species that the Park provides habitat for.

Labour requirements for park staff: 1 staff member to replace the batteries and storage of the audio recorders once per month, and to upload the data from the recorders. This task fits within a campsite turnover workday.

External support requirements: Research team member for baseline measurement.

References: Brandes (2008); Furnas and Callas (2015); Stewart (2023)

Fish Species Richness

Theme	Parameter	Cost
Ecosystem component	Biodiversity	\$\$\$

Description: Fish have an important role in the food chain and nutrient cycling. Fish species richness measures the number of fish species present in the reservoir at the time of measurement. This information is important for assessing biodiversity and making sure that species populations remain stable over time.

Frequency of measurement	Required equipment
Every 5 years	Boat, sampling supplies (assembled by the research team)

Summary of methods: Ten sites will be selected to measure fish species richness. This will be done using eDNA gathered from water samples. Surface water samples will be taken in the nearshore zone (<10m from shore). At each sample site, three subsamples and one field negative control will be taken. Water samples will be filtered in site then preserved before being sent out to a laboratory for community biodiversity assessment. Sampling will be taken in the spring or fall, when the water column is thermally mixed.

External support requirements: Research team member, lab for analysis.

References: García-Machado et al. (2023)

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